

A New Recurrent Formula of Prime Numbers and New Conjectures about Goldbach's Conjecture and Twin Prime Conjecture

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November 2024

1 Summary

In this article we will discuss and show a new formula that constructs the Set of Prime Numbers in a recursive and strictly increasing manner, as well as two new conjectures arising from said formula, which hypothetically and respectively propose a way to construct in a recursive and strictly increasing manner the set of all pairs of twin primes, and given any even number greater than 2, locate a pair of primes whose sum effectively gives such a given even number. Therefore, if such conjectures turned out to be true, the truth of both the **Goldbach Conjecture** and the **Twin Prime Conjecture** would be immediately demonstrated.

The aforementioned new formula that we will discuss and show in this article is defined as follows:

Gustavo's Theorem:

If we denote by p_j the j -th prime number, then the following is true:

$$p_1 = 2$$

$$p_2 = 3$$

$$p_{n+1} - p_n = \frac{M}{2} - \max_{(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in D} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right), \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \cap [2, +\infty[$$

Where:

$$M = \prod_{i=1}^n p_i$$

$$D = \mathbb{Z}^n \bigcap \bigtimes_{i=1}^n [1, p_i - 1]$$

$$T(t_1, \dots, t_n) = -p_n + \sum_{j=1}^n t_j \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-1}.$$

From this formula, conceiving each t_j as a residue modulo p_j , the following two conjectures can be intuitively formulated, which deal respectively with the Twin Prime Conjecture and the Goldbach Conjecture:

Conjecture 1 (About the Twin Prime Conjecture):

If $n \geq 2$

$$M = \prod_{i=1}^n p_i$$

$$D' = \mathbb{Z}^n \bigcap \bigtimes_{i=1}^n [1, p_i - 1] \setminus \{2\}$$

$$T(t_1, \dots, t_n) = -p_n + \sum_{j=1}^n t_j \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-1}$$

and

$$\mathbf{p} = p_n + \frac{M}{2} - \max_{(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in D'} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right)$$

So both $\mathbf{p}$ and $\mathbf{p} - 2$ are prime numbers.

Conjecture 2 (About Goldbach's Conjecture):

If $n \geq 5$

$r = \pi(\sqrt{2n})$, where $\pi(x)$ is Prime Number Counter Function

$$M^* = \prod_{i=1}^r p_i$$

$$D^* = \mathbb{Z}^r \bigcap \bigtimes_{i=1}^r [1, p_i - 1] \setminus \{2n \bmod p_i\}$$

$$T(t_1, \dots, t_r) = -p_r + \sum_{j=1}^r t_j \left(\frac{M^*}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-1}$$

and

$$\mathbf{p}^* = p_r + \frac{M^*}{2} - \max_{(t_1, \dots, t_r) \in D^*} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M^*}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M^*}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_r)}{M^*}\right)$$

So both $\mathbf{p}^*$ and $2n - \mathbf{p}^*$ are prime numbers.

2 Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to introduce a novel recursive construction of prime numbers that offers a fresh perspective on their distribution and properties. Specifically, this approach aims to provide a unified framework to address both the Twin Primes Conjecture and Goldbach's Conjecture simultaneously. By leveraging the recursive nature of the construction, this work seeks to uncover deeper insights into these longstanding problems in number theory.

As we have already observed, the formula for prime numbers that will be demonstrated in this article allows us to formulate two new conjectures that propose respectively a possible way to construct infinite pairs of twin primes, and given any fixed even number, to find a pair of prime numbers whose sum effectively gives said fixed even number; and all that apart from the fact that such a formula clearly provides an expression for the difference between two consecutive prime numbers in terms of a trigonometric polynomial, which constitutes another indication and clue that such a difference is in fact infinitely repetitive in all its values, since trigonometric polynomials have cyclic behavior.

That is, thanks to **Gustavo's Theorem**, solving both the **Twin Prime Conjecture** and the **Goldbach's Conjecture** is probably equivalent to solving discrete optimization problems of a trigonometric polynomial.

That is, this theorem, apart from providing a new formula that constructs the set of prime numbers recursively and strictly increasing, allows a new and different approach to try to solve the Twin Prime Conjecture and the Goldbach Conjecture.

It is also worth noting that this **Gustavo's Theorem** not only constitutes a link between two different branches of Mathematics such as Number Theory and Optimization Theory, but also constitutes a direct application of a powerful postulate rarely used in Number Theory, which in this case is **Bertrand's Postulate**, whose statement is the following:

Bertrand's Postulate: For every natural number $n > 1$, there is always at least one prime p such that $n < p < 2n$.

This postulate will be used for the demonstration of Gustavo's Theorem, that is, for the deduction of the main formula of this article.

Finally, after demonstrating the veracity of this main formula, some **specific examples** will be discussed to illustrate the theoretical strength and utility of this formula, as well as of the two new conjectures mentioned above.

3 Proof of Gustavo's Theorem

First of all, to carry out our demonstration, we are going to state and prove another small theorem which is nothing more than another formulation of the **Sieve of Eratosthenes**. Its statement and demonstration are described below:

Theorem 1 (Sieve of Eratosthenes):

Let $p \in \mathbb{N}$, $r \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $r \geq \sqrt{p}$. Then, p is prime if and only if the set $\{q \text{ prime} : q \mid p, q \neq p \wedge q \leq r\} = \emptyset$.

Proof. ($\Rightarrow$) Let $A = \{q \text{ prime} : q \mid p, q \neq p \wedge q \leq r\}$. Suppose for contradiction that $A \neq \emptyset$; then there exists $q \in \mathbb{P}$ such that $q \mid p$, $q \neq p$, and $q \leq r$.

Since p is prime and divisible by q (with q also being prime), we must have $q = p$, which is a contradiction because $q \neq p$. Thus, $A = \emptyset$.

($\Leftarrow$) Now, suppose $A = \emptyset$. For contradiction, assume p is not prime. Then there exists $q \in \mathbb{P}$ such that $q \mid p$ and $1 < q < p$. Given that $A = \emptyset$, we have $q \notin A$, implying that $q > r \geq \sqrt{p}$. Therefore, $q > \sqrt{p}$, which means $q^2 > p$.

Since $q \mid p$ and $1 < q < p$, there exists $d \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $1 < d < p$ and $p = q \cdot d$. Thus $q = \frac{p}{d}$, This implies that

$$\frac{p^2}{d^2} > p,$$

so we have $p > d^2$, therefore $\sqrt{p} > d > 1$. Since $d > 1$, there exists $p_0 \in \mathbb{P}$ such that $p_0 \mid d$, with $p_0 \leq d < \sqrt{p} \leq r$. Given that $d \mid p$ and $p_0 \mid d$, it follows that $p_0 \mid p$.

Since $d < p$, this implies $p_0 < p$, so $p_0 \neq p$. Thus, we guarantee that $p_0 \in A = \emptyset$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, we conclude that p is prime.

And so, we conclude the proof.

□

Now that we have proved **theorem 1**, we proceed to state and prove a second theorem that will also be useful to prove our main result. Its statement and proof are described below:

Theorem 2 (Existence of New Recursive Formula for Prime Numbers):

Let $\{p_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be the sequence of prime numbers, then

$$p_1 = 2,$$

$$p_2 = 3,$$

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2 : p_{n+1} = \min_{(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in D} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \cdot t_j \right) - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \cdot t_j \right) - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \right),$$

where:

$$M = \prod_{i=1}^n p_i,$$

$$D = \{(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in \mathbb{N}^n \mid \forall i = 1, \dots, n : 1 \leq t_i \leq p_i - 1\};$$

$$\lfloor \cdot \rfloor : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z} \text{ such that } \lfloor x \rfloor = \max\{k \in \mathbb{Z} : k \leq x\}.$$

Proof. Let $f : D \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ such that

$$f(t_1, \dots, t_n) = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \cdot t_j \right) - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \cdot t_j \right) - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor$$

We define a set B such that $B := f(D)$. We observe that $|D| = \prod_{i=1}^n (p_i - 1) < \infty$, therefore

$|B| = |f(D)| \leq |D| < \infty$, so the set B is finite and non-empty, thus we ensure that B has a minimum value, i.e., there exists $z \in \mathbb{Z} : z = \min B$. Therefore

we need to prove that $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2 : p_{n+1} = z = \min B$. To do this, we proceed as follows:

Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $n \geq 2$. By **theorem 1**, we have that

$$\forall r \geq \sqrt{(p_{n+1})} : A(r) = \{q \text{ prime} : q \mid p_{n+1}, q \neq p_{n+1} \wedge q \leq r\} = \emptyset.$$

By **Bertrand's postulate**, we can guarantee that

$$p_{n+1} < 2 \cdot p_n \Rightarrow \sqrt{(p_{n+1})} < \sqrt{(2 \cdot p_n)} \leq \sqrt{(p_n \cdot p_n)} = \sqrt{((p_n)^2)} = p_n,$$

thus we have that $p_n \geq \sqrt{(p_{n+1})}$. Then taking $r = p_n$, we have that the set

$$A(p_n) = \{q \text{ prime} : q \mid p_{n+1}, q \neq p_{n+1} \wedge q \leq p_n\} = \emptyset,$$

thus this guarantees that $\forall j = 1, \dots, n : p_j \nmid p_{n+1}$.

Therefore $\exists (t_1^0, \dots, t_n^0) \in D$ such that

$$p_{n+1} \equiv t_1^0 \pmod{p_1}$$

⋮

$$p_{n+1} \equiv t_n^0 \pmod{p_n}.$$

Then by the **Chinese Remainder Theorem**, we have that:

$$p_{n+1} \equiv \sum_{j=1}^n \left(t_j^0 \cdot b_j \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right) \right) \pmod{M}$$

for all $b_j \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $\forall j = 1, \dots, n : b_j \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$.

Since $\forall j = 1, \dots, n : \left(\frac{M}{p_j}, p_j \right) = 1$, **Fermat's Little Theorem** guarantees that

$$\forall j = 1, \dots, n : \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j} \text{ so } \forall j = 1, \dots, n : \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-2} \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right) \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}.$$

Thus, in particular if $\forall j = 1, \dots, n : b_j = \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-2}$, then by the **Chinese Remainder Theorem** we guarantee:

$$p_{n+1} \equiv \sum_{j=1}^n \left(t_j^0 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-2} \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right) \right) = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(t_j^0 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-1} \right) \pmod{M}.$$

Thus we ensure that $\exists (t_1^0, \dots, t_n^0) \in D$ and an integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that

$$p_{n+1} = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(t_j^0 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-1} \right) + M \cdot k.$$

Now let $Q = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(t_j^0 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-1} \right)$. **Bertrand's postulate** guarantees that:

$$p_n < p_{n+1} < 2 \cdot p_n \Rightarrow p_n < Q + M \cdot k < 2 \cdot p_n.$$

$$\Rightarrow p_n - Q < M \cdot k < 2 \cdot p_n - Q$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{p_n - Q}{M} < k < \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M}.$$

Therefore, we ensure that

$$\left\lceil \frac{p_n - Q}{M} \right\rceil \leq k \leq \left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M} \right\rfloor.$$

Thus, we have

$$\left\lceil \frac{p_n - Q}{M} \right\rceil \leq \left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M} \right\rfloor.$$

Now, applying **the basic properties of the floor functions and ceil functions**, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
\left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M} \right\rfloor - \left\lceil \frac{p_n - Q}{M} \right\rceil &= \left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M} \right\rfloor - \left(- \left\lfloor \frac{Q - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \right) \\
&= \left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M} \right\rfloor + \left\lfloor \frac{Q - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \leq \left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M} + \frac{Q - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \\
&= \left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q + Q - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{p_n}{M} \right\rfloor = 0, \text{ because } \forall n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2 : p_n < M.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus we guarantee that

$$\left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M} \right\rfloor - \left\lceil \frac{p_n - Q}{M} \right\rceil \leq 0, \text{ which is equivalent to } \left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M} \right\rfloor \leq \left\lceil \frac{p_n - Q}{M} \right\rceil$$

So therefore, it is concluded that

$$\left\lfloor \frac{2 \cdot p_n - Q}{M} \right\rfloor = \left\lceil \frac{p_n - Q}{M} \right\rceil.$$

This then ensures that $k = \left\lceil \frac{p_n - Q}{M} \right\rceil = - \left\lfloor \frac{Q - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor$.

Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
p_{n+1} &= Q - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{Q - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \cdot t_j^0 \right) - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \cdot t_j^0 \right) - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \\
&= f(t_1^0, \dots, t_n^0) \in f(D) = B.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus $p_{n+1} \in B$, so we have that $p_{n+1} \geq z = \min B$.

Now suppose, for the sake of contradiction, that $p_{n+1} > z = \min B$. This implies that p_{n+1} cannot be a lower bound of the set $f(D)$. Therefore, there exists $(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1) \in D$ such that

$$p_{n+1} > f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1) = H - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{H - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor, \quad \text{where } H = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(t_j^1 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j - 1} \right).$$

Then, since

$$\left\lfloor \frac{H - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \leq \frac{H - p_n}{M},$$

this implies that

$$H - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{H - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \geq H - M \cdot \frac{H - p_n}{M} = H - (H - p_n) = p_n.$$

Thus, we guarantee that $p_{n+1} > f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1) = H - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{H - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \geq p_n$.

Now we will prove that $f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1)$ is a prime number; to do so, we will proceed by contradiction.

Assume that $f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1)$ is not prime. Now, by **Bertrand's postulate**, we have

$$\sqrt{f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1)} < \sqrt{p_{n+1}} < \sqrt{2 \cdot p_n} \leq \sqrt{(p_n \cdot p_n)} = \sqrt{(p_n)^2} = p_n.$$

Then, by **Theorem 1**, we guarantee that

$$\{q \text{ prime} : q \mid f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1), q \neq f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1) \wedge q \leq p_n\} \neq \emptyset.$$

This then ensures that there exists a prime $q \in \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$:

$$q \mid f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1) \wedge q \neq f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1).$$

Therefore,

$$q \mid f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1) = H - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{H - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor.$$

Now, as $q \in \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$, this implies that $q \mid M$.

$$\text{Therefore, we have that } q \mid H = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(t_j^1 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \right).$$

Since $q \in \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$, this guarantees that there exists $s \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $q = p_s$. It is clear that

$$\forall j \neq s, j = 1, \dots, n : p_s = q \mid \left(t_j^1 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \right) \text{ and } \left(\left(\frac{M}{p_s} \right)^{p_s-1}, p_s \right) = 1. \text{ Thus, since } q \mid H, \text{ this guarantees that}$$

$$p_s = q \mid \left(t_s^1 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_s} \right)^{p_s-1} \right).$$

Fermat's Little Theorem assures that $\left(\frac{M}{p_s} \right)^{p_s-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_s}$.

Thus, $\left(\frac{M}{p_s} \right)^{p_s-1} \cdot t_s^1 \equiv t_s^1 \pmod{p_s}$, so since $p_s = q \mid \left(t_s^1 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_s} \right)^{p_s-1} \right)$, this guarantees that $p_s \mid t_s^1$. But this is a contradiction because $1 \leq t_s^1 \leq p_s - 1$.

Thus, we guarantee that $f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1)$ is indeed a prime number.

Since $p_{n+1} > f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1) = H - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{H - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \geq p_n$, this implies that

$$f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1) = p_n,$$

therefore $p_n \mid f(t_1^1, \dots, t_n^1) = H - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{H - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor$. Now, since $p_n \in \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$, this implies that $p_n \mid M$.

Therefore, we have that

$$p_n \mid H = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(t_j^1 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \right).$$

It is clear that $\forall j \neq n, j = 1, \dots, n : p_n \mid \left(t_j^1 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \right)$ and $\left(\left(\frac{M}{p_n} \right)^{p_n-1}, p_n \right) = 1$.

Since $p_n \mid H$, this guarantees that $p_n \mid \left(t_n^1 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_n} \right)^{p_n-1} \right)$.

Fermat's Little Theorem assures that $\left(\frac{M}{p_n}\right)^{p_n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_n}$.

Thus, $\left(\frac{M}{p_n}\right)^{p_n-1} \cdot t_n^1 \equiv t_n^1 \pmod{p_n}$, so since $p_n \mid \left(t_n^1 \cdot \left(\frac{M}{p_n}\right)^{p_n-1}\right)$, this guarantees that $p_n \mid t_n^1$. But this is a contradiction because $1 \leq t_n^1 \leq p_n - 1$. Thus, we guarantee that $p_{n+1} \leq z = \min B$, so we ensure that $p_{n+1} = \min f(D)$.

This proves the **Theorem 2**, and we conclude that:

If $\{p_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is the sequence of prime numbers, then

$$p_1 = 2, \quad p_2 = 3,$$

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2 : p_{n+1} = \min_{(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in D} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \cdot t_j \right) - M \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \cdot t_j \right) - p_n}{M} \right\rfloor \right),$$

where

$$M = \prod_{i=1}^n p_i,$$

$$D = \{(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in \mathbb{N}^n \text{ such that } \forall i = 1, \dots, n : 1 \leq t_i \leq p_i - 1\},$$

$$\lfloor \cdot \rfloor : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z} \text{ such that } \lfloor x \rfloor = \max\{k \in \mathbb{Z} : k \leq x\}.$$

Well, now that we have proven these two theorems, we are finally able to present the achievement of the proof of a substantial improvement to **Theorem 2**, that is, the proof of **Gustavo's Theorem**.

Achieving the demonstration of Gustavo's Theorem:

For $\forall n \in [2, \infty) \cap \mathbb{N}$ and $(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in D$, we will do the following:

If $T(t_1, \dots, t_n) = -p_n + \sum_{j=1}^n t_j \left(\frac{M}{p_j}\right)^{p_j-1}$, then using the property of the **modulus operator** which states

that $x \bmod y = x - y \left\lfloor \frac{x}{y} \right\rfloor$, $\forall (x, y) \in \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}^+$, we deduce that

$$f(t_1, \dots, t_n) = T(t_1, \dots, t_n) + p_n - (T(t_1, \dots, t_n) - T(t_1, \dots, t_n) \bmod M) = p_n + T(t_1, \dots, t_n) \bmod M.$$

Now, if we define a sequence x_j as: $x_j = j \bmod M$, then we can perfectly define its respective

Discrete Fourier Transform X_k , which is given by the following expression:

$$X_k = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} x_j e^{-\frac{2\pi i}{M}kj} \quad \text{with } k = 0, \dots, M-1$$

Therefore, if $w_k = e^{-\frac{2\pi i}{M}k}$, then we have:

$$X_k = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} j w_k^j$$

Therefore, first of all, if $k = 0$, we have that:

$$X_0 = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} j w_0^j = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} j = \sum_{j=1}^{M-1} j = \frac{(M-1)M}{2}$$

Meanwhile, for $k \in \{1, \dots, M-1\}$ it is true that:

$$w_k \neq 1$$

Therefore,

$$\sum_{j=0}^{M-1} w_k^j = \frac{1 - w_k^M}{1 - w_k} = 0$$

And therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} X_k &= \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} j w_k^j = \sum_{j=1}^{M-1} j w_k^j = \sum_{j=0}^{M-2} (j+1) w_k^{j+1} = \sum_{j=0}^{M-2} j w_k^{j+1} + \sum_{j=0}^{M-2} w_k^{j+1} = \left(w_k \sum_{j=0}^{M-2} j w_k^j \right) + (-1) \\ &= w_k (X_k - w_k^{M-1} (M-1)) - 1 = w_k X_k - w_k^M (M-1) - 1 = w_k X_k - (1)(M-1) - 1 = w_k X_k - M \end{aligned}$$

So then, clearing X_k , we finally have that:

$$X_k = \frac{M}{w_k - 1} \quad \text{with } k = 1, \dots, M-1$$

Therefore, applying the **Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform**, we have that:

$$x_j = j \bmod M = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=0}^{M-1} X_k e^{\frac{2\pi i}{M} k j} = \frac{M-1}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \frac{e^{\frac{2\pi i}{M} k j}}{w_k - 1} = \frac{M-1}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \frac{e^{\frac{2\pi i}{M} k j}}{e^{-\frac{2\pi i}{M} k} - 1}$$

Now, since x_j is a sequence of real numbers and simplifying we have that:

$$x_j = \operatorname{Re}(x_j) = j \bmod M = \frac{M-1}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \left(\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{e^{\frac{2\pi i}{M} k j}}{e^{-\frac{2\pi i}{M} k} - 1} \right) \right) = \frac{M-1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \left(\cos \left(\frac{2\pi k j}{M} \right) + \cot \left(\frac{\pi k}{M} \right) \sin \left(\frac{2\pi k j}{M} \right) \right)$$

Then, since $\sum_{j=1}^n t_j \left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \not\equiv p_n \pmod{p_n}$, then we have that $\sum_{j=1}^n t_j \left(\frac{M}{p_j} \right)^{p_j-1} \not\equiv p_n \pmod{M}$,

and therefore, $T(t_1, \dots, t_n) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{M}$.

So this implies that:

$$e^{\frac{2\pi i}{M} T(t_1, \dots, t_n)} \neq 1$$

Therefore,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \left(\cos \left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M} \right) \right) = -1 + \operatorname{Re} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{M-1} e^{\frac{2\pi i}{M} k T(t_1, \dots, t_n)} \right) = -1 + \operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{1 - e^{2\pi i T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}}{1 - e^{\frac{2\pi i}{M} T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}} \right) = -1 + 0 = -1$$

Therefore it is guaranteed that:

$$f(t_1, \dots, t_n) = p_n + T(t_1, \dots, t_n) \bmod M =$$

$$\begin{aligned} & p_n + \frac{M-1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \left(\cos\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right) + \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right) \right) \\ &= p_n + \frac{M-1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \left(-1 + \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \left(\cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right) \right) \right) \\ &= p_n + \frac{M}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Then, since

$$\begin{aligned} \cot\left(\frac{\pi(M-k)}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi(M-k) \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right) &= \cot\left(\pi - \frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(2\pi \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n) - \frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right) \\ &= \left(-\cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right)\right) \left(-\sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right)\right) = \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right), \quad \text{for } k = 1, \dots, \frac{M}{2} - 1. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{and } \cot\left(\frac{\pi\left(\frac{M}{2}\right)}{M}\right) = \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = 0,$$

We have that:

$$f(t_1, \dots, t_n) = p_n + \frac{M}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \left(2 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right) \right)$$

$$= p_n + \frac{M}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right)$$

Therefore, by **theorem 2** we conclude that:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{n+1} = \min f(D) &= \min_{(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in D} \left(p_n + \frac{M}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right) \right) \\ &= p_n + \frac{M}{2} + \min_{(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in D} \left(- \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right) \right) \\ &= p_n + \frac{M}{2} - \max_{(t_1, \dots, t_n) \in D} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, \dots, t_n)}{M}\right) \end{aligned}$$

And this is how we have completed the proof of **Gustavo's Theorem**.

4 Examples about Gustavo's Theorem

Example 1

In this example we will construct the prime number **13** from the prime numbers that precede it, using our formula derived from **Gustavo's Theorem**.

To do this we will use **Wolfram Mathematica 14 software**, as follows:

1. In this case, $n = 5$. Therefore, we first proceed to build the number M and the function

$T(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5)$:

```
In[1]:= M = ∏i=15 Prime[i]
```

```
Out[1]= 2310
```

```
In[2]:= T[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_] :=
  -Prime[5] + t1 * (M / Prime[1])Prime[1]-1 + t2 * (M / Prime[2])Prime[2]-1 + t3 * (M / Prime[3])Prime[3]-1 +
  t4 * (M / Prime[4])Prime[4]-1 + t5 * (M / Prime[5])Prime[5]-1
```

2. Now we build the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5)$:

```
In[3]:= f[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_] :=
```

$$\text{Prime}[5] + \frac{M}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \left(\text{Cot}\left[\frac{\pi * k}{M}\right] * \text{Sin}\left[\frac{2 * \pi * k * T[t1, t2, t3, t4, t5]}{M}\right] \right)$$

3. Finally we calculate the minimum of the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5)$ over D :

```
In[5]:= combinaciones =
  Select[Tuples[{Range[1, 1], Range[1, 2], Range[1, 4], Range[1, 6], Range[1, 10]}],
  Element[#, Integers] &];

In[6]:= imagenes = f@@@ combinaciones; (*Evaluate f for each combination*)

In[7]:= minimo = Min[imagenes];

In[8]:= minimo
Out[8]= 13.
```

And as we can see: the final result of calculating this minimum is indeed 13, just as we expected!

Example 2

In this example we will construct the prime number 17 from the prime numbers that precede it, using our formula derived from **Gustavo's Theorem**.

To do this we will use **Wolfram Mathematica 14 software**, as follows:

1. In this case, $n = 6$. Therefore, we first proceed to build the number M and the function

$$T(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6):$$

The screenshot shows the Wolfram Mathematica 14 interface. The input cell contains the following code:

```
In[1]:= M = Product[Prime[i], {i, 1, 6}]
```

The output cell shows the result:

```
Out[1]= 30030
```

The next input cell defines the function T:

```
In[2]:= T[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_, t6_] :=
  -Prime[6] + t1 * (M/Prime[1])^(Prime[1]-1) + t2 * (M/Prime[2])^(Prime[2]-1) + t3 * (M/Prime[3])^(Prime[3]-1) +
  t4 * (M/Prime[4])^(Prime[4]-1) + t5 * (M/Prime[5])^(Prime[5]-1) + t6 * (M/Prime[6])^(Prime[6]-1)
```

2. Now we build the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6)$:

The screenshot shows the Wolfram Mathematica 14 interface. The input cell contains the following code:

```
In[3]:= f[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_, t6_] :=
  Prime[6] + M/2 - Sum[Cot[Pi*k/M] * Sin[2*Pi*k*T[t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6]/M], {k, 1, M/2-1}]
```

3. Finally we calculate the minimum of the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6)$ over D :

```

In[4]:= combinaciones =
      Select[Tuples[{Range[1, 1], Range[1, 2], Range[1, 4], Range[1, 6], Range[1, 10],
      |selecc... |tuplas |rango |rango |rango |rango |rango
      Range[1, 12]}], Element[#, Integers] &];
      |rango |pertenece a |números enteros

In[5]:= imagenes = f@@@ combinaciones; (*Evaluate f for each combination*)

In[6]:= minimo = Min[imagenes];
      |mínimo

In[7]:= minimo
Out[7]= 17

```

And as we can see: the final result of calculating this minimum is indeed 17, just as we expected!

5 Examples about Conjecture 1

Example 3

In this example, from the **first six prime numbers** we are going to build a **pair of twin prime numbers** greater than or equal to the **sixth prime number**, using the formula stated in **Conjecture 1**:

1. In this case, $n = 6$. Therefore, we first proceed to build the number M and the function

$$T(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6):$$

The screenshot shows a Mathematica notebook interface. The input cell contains the following code:

```

In[1]:= M = Product[Prime[i], {i, 1, 6}]

```

The output cell shows the result:

```

Out[1]= 30030

```

The next input cell defines the function T:

```

In[2]:= T[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_, t6_] :=
  -Prime[6] + t1 * (M/Prime[1])^(Prime[1]-1) + t2 * (M/Prime[2])^(Prime[2]-1) + t3 * (M/Prime[3])^(Prime[3]-1) +
  t4 * (M/Prime[4])^(Prime[4]-1) + t5 * (M/Prime[5])^(Prime[5]-1) + t6 * (M/Prime[6])^(Prime[6]-1)

```

The function T is defined as a sum of terms, each representing a prime number multiplied by a power of the product of the first six primes (M) divided by that prime. The first term is negative, while the others are positive.

2. Now we build the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6)$:

```
In[3]:= f[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_, t6_] :=
Prime[6] +  $\frac{M}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \left( \text{Cot}\left[\frac{\pi * k}{M}\right] * \text{Sin}\left[\frac{2 * \pi * k * T[t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6]}{M}\right] \right)$ 
```

3. Finally we calculate the minimum of the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6)$ over D' to find p :

```
In[4]:= Minimize[{f[t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6],
|minimiza
(1 ≤ t1 ≤ 1 && t1 ≠ 2) && (1 ≤ t2 ≤ 2 && t2 ≠ 2) && (1 ≤ t3 ≤ 4 && t3 ≠ 2) &&
(1 ≤ t4 ≤ 6 && t4 ≠ 2) && (1 ≤ t5 ≤ 10 && t5 ≠ 2) && (1 ≤ t6 ≤ 12 && t6 ≠ 2) &&
Element[{t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6}, Integers]}, {t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6}]
|pertenece a |números enteros

Out[4]= {19, {t1 → 1, t2 → 1, t3 → 4, t4 → 5, t5 → 8, t6 → 6}}
```

And as we can see, our final result is 19, that is, a prime number, and we can clearly also see that indeed $19 - 2 = 17$, that is, another prime number.

Therefore, from the first six prime numbers we have built the pair of twin prime numbers (17, 19), which implies that our **conjecture 1** is fulfilled for this case when $n = 6$.

Example 4

In this example, from the **first eight prime numbers** we are going to build a **pair of twin prime numbers** greater than or equal to the **eighth prime number**, using the formula stated in

Conjecture 1:

1. In this case, $n = 8$. Therefore, we first proceed to build the number M and the function

$$T(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6, t_7, t_8):$$

```

In[1]:= M =  $\prod_{i=1}^8 \text{Prime}[i]$ 
Out[1]= 9699690

In[2]:= T[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_, t6_, t7_, t8_] :=
-Prime[8] + t1 *  $\left(\frac{M}{\text{Prime}[1]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[1]-1}$  + t2 *  $\left(\frac{M}{\text{Prime}[2]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[2]-1}$  + t3 *  $\left(\frac{M}{\text{Prime}[3]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[3]-1}$  +
t4 *  $\left(\frac{M}{\text{Prime}[4]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[4]-1}$  + t5 *  $\left(\frac{M}{\text{Prime}[5]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[5]-1}$  + t6 *  $\left(\frac{M}{\text{Prime}[6]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[6]-1}$  +
t7 *  $\left(\frac{M}{\text{Prime}[7]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[7]-1}$  + t8 *  $\left(\frac{M}{\text{Prime}[8]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[8]-1}$ 

```

2. Now we build the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6, t_7, t_8)$:

```

In[3]:= f[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_, t6_, t7_, t8_] :=
Prime[8] +  $\frac{M}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M}{2}-1} \left( \text{Cot}\left[\frac{\pi * k}{M}\right] * \text{Sin}\left[\frac{2 * \pi * k * T[t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7, t8]}{M}\right] \right)$ 

```

3. Finally we calculate the minimum of the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6, t_7, t_8)$ over D' to find p :

```

In[6]:= Minimize[{f[t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7, t8],
minimiza
(1 ≤ t1 ≤ 1 && t1 ≠ 2) && (1 ≤ t2 ≤ 2 && t2 ≠ 2) && (1 ≤ t3 ≤ 4 && t3 ≠ 2) &&
(1 ≤ t4 ≤ 6 && t4 ≠ 2) && (1 ≤ t5 ≤ 10 && t5 ≠ 2) && (1 ≤ t6 ≤ 12 && t6 ≠ 2) &&
(1 ≤ t7 ≤ 16 && t7 ≠ 2) && (1 ≤ t8 ≤ 18 && t8 ≠ 2) &&
Element[{t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7, t8}, Integers]}, {t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7, t8}]
pertenece a números enteros
Out[6]= {31, {t1 → 1, t2 → 1, t3 → 1, t4 → 3, t5 → 9, t6 → 5, t7 → 14, t8 → 12}}

```

And as we can see, our final result is 31, that is, a prime number, and we can clearly also see that indeed $31 - 2 = 29$, that is, another prime number.

Therefore, from the first eight prime numbers we have built the pair of twin prime numbers (29, 31), which implies that our **conjecture 1** is fulfilled for this case when $n = 8$.

6 Examples about Conjecture 2

Example 5

In this example we will find, using the formula posed in **Conjecture 2**, a pair of prime numbers whose sum results in 40.

1. In this case $n = 20$. Therefore, we first build the numbers r and M^* :

```
In[1]:= r = PrimePi[ $\sqrt{40}$ ]
```

```
Out[1]= 3
```

```
In[2]:= M* =  $\prod_{i=1}^r$  Prime[i]
```

```
Out[2]= 30
```

2. Now we build the functions $T(t_1, t_2, t_3)$ and

$$f(t_1, t_2, t_3) = p_3 + \frac{M^*}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M^*}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M^*}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, t_2, t_3)}{M^*}\right):$$

```
In[3]:= T[t1_, t2_, t3_] := -Prime[3] + t1 *  $\left(\frac{M^*}{\text{Prime}[1]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[1]-1}$  + t2 *  $\left(\frac{M^*}{\text{Prime}[2]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[2]-1}$  +  
t3 *  $\left(\frac{M^*}{\text{Prime}[3]}\right)^{\text{Prime}[3]-1}$ 
```

```
In[4]:= f[t1_, t2_, t3_] := Prime[3] +  $\frac{M^*}{2}$  -  $\sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M^*}{2}-1}$   $\left(\text{Cot}\left[\frac{\pi * k}{M^*}\right] * \text{Sin}\left[\frac{2 * \pi * k * T[t1, t2, t3]}{M^*}\right]\right)$ 
```

3. Finally we calculate the minimum of the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3)$ over D^* to find $\mathbf{p}^*$:

```
In[11]:= N[  
  Minimize[  
    {f[t1, t2, t3], (1 <= t1 <= 1 && t1 != Mod[40, Prime[1]]) &&  
    (1 <= t2 <= 2 && t2 != Mod[40, Prime[2]]) && (1 <= t3 <= 4 && t3 != Mod[40, Prime[3]]) &&  
    Element[{t1, t2, t3}, Integers]}, {t1, t2, t3}]  
Out[11]= {11., {t1 -> 1., t2 -> 2., t3 -> 1.}}
```

And as we can see, our final result is **11**, that is, a prime number, and we can clearly also see that indeed $40 - 11 = 29$, that is, another prime number.

Therefore, we have found a pair of prime numbers whose sum is equal to **40**, which implies that our **conjecture 2** is fulfilled for this case when $n = 20$.

Example 6

In this example we will find, using the formula posed in **Conjecture 2**, a pair of prime numbers whose sum results in **360**.

1. In this case $n = 180$. Therefore, we first build the numbers r and M^* :

```
In[1]:= r = PrimePi [√360]
           [función pi de primos]
```

```
Out[1]= 7
```

```
In[2]:= M* = ∏ Prime [i]
           i=1 [número prim]
```

```
Out[2]= 510510
```

2. Now we build the functions $T(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6, t_7)$ and

$$f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6, t_7) = p_7 + \frac{M^*}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{M^*}{2}-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi k}{M^*}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi k \cdot T(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6, t_7)}{M^*}\right):$$

```
In[3]:= T[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_, t6_, t7_] :=
  -Prime[7] + t1 * (M*/Prime[1])^Prime[1]-1 + t2 * (M*/Prime[2])^Prime[2]-1 + t3 * (M*/Prime[3])^Prime[3]-1 +
  t4 * (M*/Prime[4])^Prime[4]-1 + t5 * (M*/Prime[5])^Prime[5]-1 + t6 * (M*/Prime[6])^Prime[6]-1 +
  t7 * (M*/Prime[7])^Prime[7]-1
```

```
In[4]:= f[t1_, t2_, t3_, t4_, t5_, t6_, t7_] :=
  Prime[7] + M*/2 - ∑ (Cot[π*k/M*] * Sin[2*π*k*T[t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7]/M*])
  [número primo] [cotangente] [seno]
```

3. Finally we calculate the minimum of the function $f(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5, t_6, t_7)$ over D^* to find $\mathbf{p}^*$:

```
In[6]:= N[
  valor numérico
  Minimize[{f[t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7],
  minimiza
    (1 ≤ t1 ≤ 1 && t1 ≠ Mod[360, Prime[1]]) && (1 ≤ t2 ≤ 2 && t2 ≠ Mod[360, Prime[2]]) &&
    (1 ≤ t3 ≤ 4 && t3 ≠ Mod[360, Prime[3]]) && (1 ≤ t4 ≤ 6 && t4 ≠ Mod[360, Prime[4]]) &&
    (1 ≤ t5 ≤ 10 && t5 ≠ Mod[360, Prime[5]]) && (1 ≤ t6 ≤ 12 && t6 ≠ Mod[360, Prime[6]]) &&
    (1 ≤ t7 ≤ 16 && t7 ≠ Mod[360, Prime[7]]) &&
  Element[{t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7}, Integers]}, {t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7}]
  pertenece a números enteros
Out[6]= {23., {t1 → 1., t2 → 2., t3 → 3., t4 → 2., t5 → 1., t6 → 10., t7 → 6.}}
```

And as we can see, our final result is 23, that is, a prime number, and we can clearly also see that indeed $360 - 23 = 337$, that is, another prime number.

```
In[7]:= 360 - 23
Out[7]= 337

In[8]:= PrimeQ[337]
  ¿primo?
Out[8]= True
```

Therefore, we have found a pair of prime numbers whose sum is equal to 360, which implies that our **conjecture 2** is fulfilled for this case when $n = 180$.

7 Conclusions

- We have found a new powerful formula that constructs the set of Prime Numbers in a recursive and strictly increasing manner, with the peculiarity that it allows us to address in a novel way the emblematic **difference between two consecutive prime numbers**.
- Thanks to this new and powerful formula, we have formulated two new powerful conjectures that allow us to approach the legendary **Goldbach and Twin Prime Conjectures** respectively, in a totally different and novel way, through the study of **trigonometric polynomials** and **discrete optimization**.
- Such is the strength of these two new conjectures that, if they were true, the veracity of both the **Goldbach Conjecture** and the **Twin Prime Conjecture** would also be automatically proven, since they respectively propose to build infinitely all the pairs of twin primes, and given an arbitrary even number greater than 2, find a pair of prime numbers whose sum results in that given even number.
- We invite the esteemed reader to find counterexamples that rule out these two new conjectures: **Conjecture 1** and **Conjecture 2**.

References

- Oscar Gustavo Carranza Tejada. *Una Construcción Recursiva del Conjunto de los Números Primos*. Available at: <http://bit.ly/3Zu4iEF>. [Accessed: November-2024].